

Android Mobile Application Tour4You

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APPROVAL SHEET

This is confirmation that we have read this article titled Android Mobile APP (Tour4You) presented by **SAAD ALI University Registration Number 186022029** and **BASHIR ULLAH KHAN University Registration Number 186022015**. We conclude that this project is of sufficient quality to ensure acceptance by Swat University for the Bachelor of Science (BS-SE) in Software Engineering.

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Mr Saad Ali
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FORWARDING SHEET

This thesis “**Tour4You Mobile Application**” submitted by **Saad Ali** and **Bashir Ullah Khan** in partial fulfillment of **BS-SE** degree has been completed under my guidance and supervision. I am satisfied with the quality of student’s project work.

Mr. Naeem Ullah

Project Report On Android Mobile Application Tour4You

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ABSTRACT

Tour4You is a full-service tour agency dedicated to providing completely reliable and practical tourism solutions by offering services for the most competitive rates in the market. At Tou4You, we expertly handle both local, national, and international tourists by providing services that include transport reservations, special and customized tour packages from simple to unique tour destinations, hotel accommodations, food, car rentals, as well as traditional shopping options, and some other events for entertainment purposes.

Our dedicated team does their best to meet customer expectations and dedicate efforts towards the ideals of personalized services, reliability, competence, and stability. Tour4You puts efforts into being representatives in major travel fairs, traditional shows, as well as local events. Keeping all the necessary factors like safety, security, comfort, ease of travel, and most importantly to gain knowledge regarding the places, we manage the very best of our tour facilities for our tours.

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DECLARATION

We declare that our dissertation "**Android Mobile APP**" is partly our own work after completing the BS in Software Engineering. The content of this article is not intended for publication in whole or in part and will not be made available to this or any other institution in the future.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

CHAPTER: 1 Introduction:	1
1.1 Introduction:	2
1.2 Mission and Vision:	3
1.3 Software Development Methodology:	3
1.4 Tools and Technologies:	4
1.4.1 Hardware:	4
1.4.2 Software:	4
CHAPTER: 2 Project Management and Plan:	5
2.1 Introduction:	6
2.2 Project Overview:	6
2.3 Project Deliverables:	6
2.4 Project Plan:	6
2.4.1 Statement of work (SOW):	7
2.4.1.1 Scope of work:	7
2.4.1.2 Location of work:	7
2.4.1.3 Deliverable schedule:	7
2.4.1.4 Acceptance criteria:	8
2.4.1.5 Special Requirements:	8
2.4.2 Resource list:	8
2.4.3 Work Breakdown Structure (WBS):	8
2.4.4 Efforts and Time Estimation:	11
2.4.5 Risk Plan:	11
CHAPTER: 3 Requirements Analysis:	13
3.1 Introduction:	14
3.2 Requirement of Tour4You Mobile Application:	14
3.3 Use Case Diagram:	14
3.4 Functional Requirement:	16

3.4.1	Admin Requirements:	16
3.4.2	User Requirements:	16
3.4.2	System Requirements:	16
3.5	Non Functional Requirements:	16
3.5.1	Database Security:	17
3.5.2	Reliability Requirements:	17
3.5.3	Usability Requirements:	17
3.5.4	Availability:	17
3.5.5	Efficiency Requirements:	17
CHAPTER: 4 Software Design:		18
4.1	Introduction:	19
4.2	Sequence Diagram:	19
4.3	Activity Diagram.....	20
4.3.1	Activity Diagram Symbols:	20
4.3.2	Activity Diagram for Tour4You:	22
4.4	Class Diagram:	23
CHAPTER: 5 Physical Database Designing:		26
5.1	Introduction:	27
5.2	Conceptual Design:	27
5.3	Physical Design:	27
5.4	Tour4You Database:	28
5.4.1	Event collection:	28
5.4.2	Guidance collection:	29
5.4.3	Hotel collection:	29
5.4.4	Nested collection in Hotel collection:	30
5.4.5	Restaurants collection:	30
5.4.6	Review collection:	31
5.4.7	Tourist Spots collection:.....	31
5.4.8	Transport collection:.....	32
5.4.9	User collection:	32

5.5	Entities of the Project:	33
5.5.1	Properties of "USER Entity":	33
5.5.2	Properties of "Transport Entity":	34
5.5.3	Properties of "Hotel Entity":	34
5.5.4	Properties of "District Entity":	35
5.5.5	Properties of "Guidance Companies Entity":	35
5.5.6	Properties of "Tourist Spot Entity":	36
5.5.7	Properties of "Hike and Track Entity":	36
5.5.8	Properties of "Restaurants Entity":	37
5.5.9	Properties of "Events Entity":	37
5.5.10	Properties of "Tour Packages Entity":	38
5.5.11	Properties of "Hotel Facilities Entity":	38
5.5.12	Properties of "Transport Facilities Entity":	39
5.6	Properties of "Transport Facilities Entity":	40
CHAPTER: 6 Project Testing:		41
6.1	Introduction:	42
6.2	Testing Functions:	42
6.3	Test Case for Admin:	42
6.3.1	Admin login form:	42
6.3.2	Admin Services Management Form:	43
6.3.3	Admin Booking Conformation:	44
6.4	Test Case for User:	44
6.4.1	User Login Form:	44
6.4.2	User Services Booking:	45
6.4.3	User Comment:	46
CHAPTER: 7 User Interface/User Guide:		47
7.1	System Installation:	48
7.2	Start Slider:	48
7.3	Home Page:	48
7.4	Navigation Drawer:	49

7.5	Login page:	50
7.6	Sign up page:	50
7.7	Hotels page:	51
7.8	Transport page:	51
7.9	Tourist spots:	52
7.10	Guidance page:	52
7.11	Events page:	53
7.12	Restaurants Page:	53
7.13	Hotel page:	54
7.14	Transport Booking page:	55
7.15	Guidance Company Booking Page:	55
7.16	Restaurant Page:	56
7.17	Search Page:	56
7.18	Our Team Page:	57
CHAPTER: 08 Tools and Technologies:		58
8.1	Introduction:	59
8.2	Flutter:	59
8.3	Dart:	59
8.4	Firebase Database:	59
8.5	Visual Studio Code:	59
8.6	Figma:	59
8.7	Adobe Illustrator:	60
CHAPTER: 09 Summary and Future Work		61
9.1	Summary:	62
9.2	Future Work:	62
References:		63

LIST OF TABLE

Table 2.1	Project Deliverable schedule:	7
Table 2.2	Project Resource List:	8
Table 2.3	Tabular Form Of WBS;	10
Table 6.1	“Admin Login Form”:	43
Table 6.2	“Admin Services Management”:	43
Table 6.3	“Admin Booking Conformation”:	44
Table 6.4	“User Login Form”:	45
Table 6.5	“User Service Booking”:	45
Table 6.6	“User Comment”:	46

LIST OF FIGURE

Figure 1.1	Iteration Model:	3
Figure 2.1	Work Breakdown Structure:	9
Figure 3.1	Use Case Diagram for Tour4You:	15
Figure 4.1	Sequence Diagram for Tour4You:	20
Figure 4.2	Activity Diagram for Tour4You:	22
Figure 4.3	Class Diagram for Tour4You:	25
Figure 5.1	Tour4You Database:	28
Figure 5.2	Event Collection:	28
Figure 5.3	Guidance Collection:	29
Figure 5.4	Hotel Collection:	29
Figure 5.5	Nested Collection in Hotel Collection:	30
Figure 5.6	Restaurant Collection:	30
Figure 5.7	Review Collection:	31
Figure 5.8	Tourist Spots Collection:	31
Figure 5.9	Transport Collection:	32
Figure 5.10	User Collection:	32
Figure 5.11	“User Entity”:	33
Figure 5.12	“Transport Entity”:	34
Figure 5.13	“Hotel Entity”:	34
Figure 5.14	“District Entity”:	35
Figure 5.15	“Guidance Companies Entity”:	35
Figure 5.16	“Tourist Spot Entity”:	36

Figure 5.17	“Hike and Track Entity”:	36
Figure 5.18	“Restaurants Entity”:	37
Figure 5.19	“Events Entity”:	37
Figure 5.20	“Tour Packages Entity”:	38
Figure 5.21	“Hotel Facilities Entity”:	38
Figure 5.22	“Transport Facilities Entity”:	39
Figure 5.23	ERD Tour4You.....	40
Figure 7.1	Start slider:	48
Figure 7.2	Home Page:	49
Figure 7.3	Navigation Drawer:	49
Figure 7.4	Login Page:	50
Figure 7.5	Signup Page:	50
Figure 7.6	Hotels Page:	51
Figure 7.7	Transport Page:	51
Figure 7.8	Tourist Spots Page:	52
Figure 7.9	Guidance Page:	52
Figure 7.10	Event Page:	53
Figure 7.11	Restaurants Page:	53
Figure 7.12	Hotel Page:	54
Figure 7.13	Transport Booking Page:	55
Figure 7.14	Guidance Company Booking Page:	55
Figure 7.15	Restaurant Page:	56
Figure 7.16	Search Page:	56
Figure 7.17	Our team page.....	57

CHAPTER 01

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction:

Now a day's tourism is very high in Swat Valley. Daily lot of people come and visit Swat Valley. During their journey, they find many difficulties like Improper Guidance, Traffic Issues, and Difficulties in Hotel booking, and even they don't have an idea of the proper route to their destination and they waste a lot of time while facing these problems. So regarding these problems we starting work on this to find proper solutions for these problems. So we are going to solve these problems via technology-based IT software (Android Mobile APP). With the help of this APP, we solve all the problems faced by tourists. In this APP the user will avail of online Hotel bookings, Transport bookings, Guidance, Daily Hotel room rates, Weather information, and so many other options.

If someone wants to visit the valley they simply open our Mobile APP and search for tourist spots in Swat. All tourist spots will appear on the screen. Further, they click on the spot whether they want to visit, like kalam. If they click on kalam all Hotels, Restaurants, and other information about kalam are appeared on the screen and then they click on the Hotels all the Hotels in kalam will appear on the screen and they select the Hotel of their choice. After clicking on the Hotel all the information about Hotel will appear like room rates, room availability, facilities, food, and prices. If the user like the hotel for staying they simply click on the book button and they will be the shifted to Hotel booking page and they reserve a room for themselves. Once the room is booked then a Map option will be shown if the user wants to use it they simply click on Get direction Button and the Map will open and a guidance line will appear from the start to their destination. All the important information/places will be present on the map, whereas mechanic shops, fuel stations, restaurants, masjids, tuck shops, etc. so they can easily visit the places where they want to go.

The main purpose of this APP is to manage the traffic in a proper way. IA the APP will help tourists and also help to promote tourism in Swat also in Pakistan. The interface and use of this APP are very easy. So everyone can use it very easily.

1.4 Tools and Technologies:

We require a certain set of tools and technologies to effectively construct the tourism Android APP (Tour4You), and we need to know what kind of tools and technologies will be applied to this system. This tool may be one created especially for our project or it may be a standard productivity tool. Our work is typically made simple by the usage of such tools and technologies. In our project, which is divided into categories based on hardware and software, the following tools and technologies are utilized.

1.4.1 Hardware:

The mention below hardware are required in this project.

Asus and Lenovo ThinkPad Intel core i5 laptops

Mobile phones

Wi-Fi

Printer

1.4.2 Software:

Here are the following software used in our project:

Visual Studio Code

Flutter

Dart

Firebase

Microsoft Office

Figma

Adobe Illustrator

Canva

Operating System (Windows 10)

CHAPTER 02

Project Management and Plan

2.1 INTRODUCTION:

The project strategies and deliverables for our APP are covered in this chapter. It provides an overview.

- Statement of work (SOW)
- Resource list
- Work breakdown structure (WBS)
- Efforts and time estimation
- Project schedule
- Risk plan

2.2 Project Overview:

We created an Android Application with the Name Tour4You in which we will provide a hotel Booking Service with price comparing, Tour packages, Customize tours and trips, transport Booking service, weather information, guidance information, and explored areas.

The main aspects of our project are:

- Tourists will book their hotel rooms very easily.
- Tourists will book transport very easily.
- Provide guidance for tourists.
- Tourists will take advantage of Map.
- No wastage of time.

2.3 Project Deliverables:

Products, design documents, training manuals, and other assets that are necessary for the project plan are examples of deliverables. The material results of a project are called deliverables. The project would be useless if there were no deliverables.

1. Project plane
2. User Manual
3. Report of Project Design
4. Software
5. Final Report

2.4 Project Plan:

The project plan defines the work that will be done on the project and who will do it. It consists of:

- a) **Statement of work (SOW):** That includes a list of all the work that will be done as well as all the products that will be generated.
- b) **Resource list:** This is a list of all the resources needed for the product, together with information on their availability.
- c) **Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) and a set of estimates.**
- d) **Efforts and Time estimations.**
- e) **Project Schedule.**
- f) **Risk Plan:** That identifies any risks that might be encountered and indicates how those risks would be handled if they occur.

2.4.1 Statement of Work (SOW):

This is a list of all the resources needed for the product, together with information on A statement of work is a comprehensive summary of all the work, accommodations, dining options, transportation, and tour information that will be developed throughout the project. It contains:

2.4.1.1 Scope of work:

This project will produce a report for clients, hotel, transportation, dining restaurants, tour packages and customize tour packages, and others.

2.4.1.2 Location of work:

Any of mentioned Android mobile device will be compatible (Samsung, Huawei, Infinix, realme, etc.).

2.4.1.3 Deliverable schedule:

Table 2.1: Deliverable Schedule

Days/Deliverable	Deliverable Description
15	Requirement gathering
15	Requirement analysis
10	Functional design
20	Interface design
50	Implementation
15	Integration
15	Testing
25	Documentation

2.4.1.4 Acceptance criteria:

Our project is quick, secure, and simple to use, it will be approved. It will be very beneficial to the user.

2.4.1.5 Special Requirements:

There are no special requirements for this APP. It will run on every android Mobile.

2.4.2 Resource list:

Resource refers to a person, piece of equipment, space, or other thing that the system being created needs but has limited presence. A system for each team member will be required while creating the system. a good, quick internet connection. Weekly meetings should be held in a separate room.

Table 2.2: Project Resource List

Resource Name	Resource Description
System	Lenovo ThinkPad core i5,
Room	Separate room for weekly meetings
Internet	Proper and fast internet connection. i.e. DSL

2.4.3 Work Breakdown Structure (WBS):

A project's breakdown into smaller parts is called a work breakdown structure (WBS), and it is deliverable-oriented. An essential project deliverable that divides the team's work into digestible chunks is a work breakdown structure.

Figure 2.1 Work Breakdown Structure

Table 2.3: Tabular form of WBS

Level	WBS Code	Element Name	Definition
1	1	Hotel Management System	All work to implement a Hotel Management System.
2	1.1	Initiation	The work to initiate the project
3	1.1.1	Develop Project Charter	Project Members to develop the Project Charter.
3	1.1.2	Requirement gathering	Gathering of information from the staff about the need for the users of the system
3	1.1.3	Requirement Analysis	A detailed analysis will be made to make sure of any mismatch.
3	1.1.4	Deliverable: Submit Project Charter	The project Charter is delivered to the Project Supervisor.
3	1.1.5	Project Supervisor Reviews Project Charter	The project Supervisor reviews the Project Charter.
3	1.1.6	Project Charter Signed/Approved	The Project Supervisor signs the Project Charter which authorizes the Project Members to move to the Planning Process.
2	1.2	Planning	The work for the planning process for the project.
3	1.2.1	Develop Project Plan	Project Members develop the project plan.
3	1.2.2	Project Members Kickoff Meeting	The planning process is officially started with a project kickoff meeting. Kickoff which includes the Project Members and Project Supervisor.
3	1.2.3	Create Project Budget	Develop Project budget Development and documentation of the For project based on plan and resources.
2	1.3	Execution	Work involved to execute the project.
3	1.3.1	Project Kickoff Meeting	Project Members conduct a formal kick-off meeting with the project Supervisor.
3	1.3.2	Verify & Validate User Requirements	The original user requirements are reviewed by the project members and then validated with the users/stakeholders.
3	1.3.3	Design System	The technical resources design the new Hotel Management system
3	1.3.4	Procure Hardware/Software	The procurement of all hardware, software, and facility needs for the project
3	1.3.5	Install Development System	Project members install a development system for testing and customization of user interfaces
3	1.3.6	Testing Phase	The system is tested with a select set of users. Here each and every component of the system is tested.

3	1.3.7	Install System	The actual system is installed and configured.
3	1.3.8	User Training	For training purposes some users are allowed to use the system.
2	1.4	Control	The work involved in the control process of the project.
3	1.4.1	Project Management	Overall project management for the project.
3	1.4.2	Project Status Meetings	Weekly team status meetings.
3	1.4.3	Risk plan	Risk management efforts as defined in the Risk Plan.
2	1.5	Closeout	The work to close out the project.
3	1.5.1	Document Lessons Learned	Project Members perform lessons learned meetings and document the lessons learned for the project.
3	1.5.2	Gain Formal Acceptance	The Project Supervisor formally accepts the project by signing the acceptance document included in the project plan.
3	1.5.3	Archive Files/Documents	All project-related files and documents are formally archived.
3	1.5.4	Handover	At the end of project completion the documentation will be handover to the Project Supervisor

2.4.4 Time Estimation and Efforts:

Based on sparse, ambiguous, and noisy data, time estimation and efforts is the process of estimating the most reasonable amount of effort (expressed in person-hours or dollars) needed to develop or maintain software.

Team Members:

- SAAD ALI
- BASHIR ULLAH KHAN

Supervisor:

NAEEM ULLAH

2.4.5 Risk Plan:

The schedule overrun is one of the most significant risks in any project, and it typically occurs in final-year projects. These activities should be kept in mind because sometimes the time allotted to another work based on estimation doesn't produce the desired results, causing schedule overruns. Changes in requirement are the other risk that is probable. During the course of a project's development lifecycle, requirements are always changing. When certain requirements can't be met in the manner we had planned, we must alter our strategy. It is extremely risky and ought to be avoided outright. The following is a list of some of the risks:

- **Any Team Member Leaves:** His work will be redistributed along with other things.

- **Virus Risk:** An appropriate antivirus program will be set up.
- **Poor Quality:** We periodically check to make sure the project is carrying out the assigned task effectively and correctly.
- **Lack of Skill:** To avoid this, platforms and tongues that are familiar to all team members are chosen (PHP).

CHAPTER: 03

SOFTWARE REQRIMENTS ANALYSIS

3.1 Introduction:

The Tour4You provides a complete Tourism Market place to local, national, and international tourists. Tour4You Application offers multiple services like (online hotel booking, transport booking, guidance services, Tour packages, Customize Tour Packages, and traditional shopping) all over Pakistan. Pakistan is one of the richest countries for tourist places in the world but unfortunately, there is no proper platform that provides all kinds of mandatory services and different types of services on a single platform. We also provide restaurant details, restaurant reservations, events details, tourists spots details, and Maps options to navigate his/her destination. The user will be able to give feedback on Tour4You and on services individually.

3.2 Requirement of Tour4You Mobile Application:

The following requirements consist of admin requirements and user requirements. The admin Requirements are about to admin in which all requirements and responsibilities are properly defined about admin. The User Requirements are about to admin in which all requirements and responsibilities are properly defined about User. Where users can see all information about tourist spots, events, hotels, restaurants, etc. Users can book a hotel room, transport, and guidance if needed according to his/her interest. Users can also reserve tour packages. The given requirements used in the Tour4You Application system are the following.

3.3 Use Case Diagram:

A UML use case diagram serves as the primary visual representation of the system/software requirements for an incomplete new software development. The desired behavior (what) is described in use cases, not the exact methods to achieve it (how). Use cases can be portrayed visually and textually once they have been defined (i.e. use case diagram). A core assumption is that use case modelling can help with system design from the perspective of the end user. It is a helpful tool for educating users about system behavior because it describes all externally observable system behavior.

The majority of use case diagrams are simple. The specifics of the use cases are not displayed:

- Only a few of the connections between use cases, actors, and systems are summarized.
- It omits displaying the sequence in which each use case's objectives are accomplished.

Case Study Diagram It is a simple illustration that is used to illustrate how data flows through an information system for businesses. The physical information stream chart shows how the coherent information stream is carried out.

Use Case Diagram

Figure 3.1 Use Case Diagram for Tour4You

3.5 Functional Requirements:

Developers must create functional criteria for their products in order to help users achieve their goals. They outline the underlying system behavior in a given situation.

Below are the functional requirements for our project.

3.5.1 Admin Requirements:

The admin can add new services (Hotel, transport, guidance, tour package, event, tourist spots, restaurant, etc.).

The service can be updated by the admin.

The services can be deleted by admin

The services can be search by admin.

The admin can manage all types of services related to Tour4You.

3.5.2 User Requirements:

The user can sign up by filling out the sign-up page.

The user can log in after validation of his/her Credentials from the database.

Users can share his/her feedback through comments.

The User can search for service of his/ her choice.

The user can use the Maps option for navigation.

The user can book the hotel, transport, tour packages, guidance, and restaurant.

The user can create customized tour packages by his / her interest.

The User can see all information about tourist spots and our services.

3.5.3 System Requirements:

Tour4You provide logout functionality to the user

Tour4You will accept valid login details to enroll on the tour4you application.

Tour4You will provide a password recovery service.

Tour4You will redirect the user to WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, etc. whenever the above-mentioned icon is pressed.

3.6 Non Functional Requirements:

A Nonfunctional requirements NFR is a need that offers criteria rather than particular behaviors that can be used to gauge how well a system performs. It is a kind of demand that is employed in

requirements engineering and systems engineering. Contrasting them are functional requirements, which specify specific activities or capabilities.

3.6.1 Database Security:

An unauthorized person cannot read and write the information and cannot access the panel and database. It should maintain the security of the client's payment method and security of all information.

3.6.2 Reliability Requirement:

Tour4You should provide a reliable environment to both tourists and service providers. The Admin is responsible to upload, delete and update new services and packages without any error.

3.6.3 Usability Requirement:

The Tour4You is designed for user-friendly environment and is easy to use. Users can use the mobile interface to use our application.

3.6.4 Availability:

Tour4You should be available for 24 hours because we provide our services on the internet so it's possible to get a reservation anytime.

3.6.5 Efficiency Requirement:

When an online package of Tours and travel is implemented customers can have reserved packages in an efficient manner.

CHAPTER: 04

SOFTWARE DESIGN

4.1 Introduction

The aim of the design phase is to come up with a solution to the issue mentioned in the requirements document. To transition from the problem domain to the solution domain, one must first do this action. The quality of the software is likely most significantly influenced by the system design, which has a significant impact on the following stages. In order to build a system later on, a model of the system must be created throughout the design process. The system design is what the generated model is referred to as. Sequence diagrams, Activity diagrams, and Class diagrams will all be covered in this section.

Class diagrams show the classes in the system together with their properties, operations (or methods), and relationships to other objects in order to depict the structure of the system. Activity diagrams are visual representation of workflows with choice, iteration, and concurrency supported by activities and actions.

4.2 Sequence Diagram:

Interaction diagrams known as UML Sequence Diagrams outline the stages necessary to carry out an operation. They show how things interact when operating within a cooperative system. The vertical axis of a sequence diagram is used to depict the time at which messages are transmitted and received. Sequence diagrams are time-focused. They are better able to represent the interaction's sequence thanks to this.

Sequence Diagrams capture:

- The conversation that occurs during a collaboration that either executes an operation or a use case (instance diagrams or generic diagrams)
- High-level interactions involving the system and its user, the system and other systems, or the system and its subsystems (sometimes known as system sequence diagrams)

SEQUENCE DIAGRAM

Figure 3.2 Sequence Diagram for Tour4You

4.3 Activity Diagram

The Activity Diagram, which is used to explain the aspects of the system, is another crucial diagram in UML. A flow chart that depicts the movement of data and program is similar to an activity diagram. The operation of the system is the name given to each activity. The flow is drawn from one operation to the next for this reason. Any form of flow is possible here. Activity diagrams use many elements, such as fork, join, etc., to regulate different sorts of flow.

4.3.1 Activity Diagram Symbols:

Initial State or Start Point:

Any activity diagram's initial action state or starting point is shown as a small filled circle and an arrow. Make sure the start point is positioned in the top left corner of the first column for activity diagrams that use swim lanes.

Action State or Activity:

An action state is a representation of an object's uninterrupted motion. A rectangle with rounded sides can be used in Smart Draw to represent an action state.

Activity Flow:

The transitions from one action state to another are shown by the action flows, also known as edges and routes. They are frequently represented with an arrowed line.

Object Flow:

Object flow describes how actions create and change objects. A creation or influence of the object is shown by an object flow arrow from an action to an object. An object flow arrow from an object to an action shows that the object is used by the current state.

Decisions and Branching:

A decision with multiple options is represented by a diamond. Add a diamond in between two activities when a choice must be made before going on to the next activity. A condition or guard expression should be used to identify the outgoing alternates. One of the paths can alternatively be marked as "else."

Final State or End Point:

The final action state is represented by an arrow leading to a filled circle nested inside another circle.

4.2.2 Activity Diagram for Tour4You

Figure 4.1 Activity Diagram for Tour4You

4.3 Class Diagram

Unlike other diagrams, the class diagram is static. It is an image of an application's static view. Class diagrams are used to visualize, describe, and document different components of a system as well as to create executable code for software programs. A class diagram shows a class's characteristics, actions, and restrictions on the system. Class diagrams are often used in the modelling of object-oriented systems because they are the only UML diagrams that can be immediately translated to object-oriented languages.

A variety of classes, interfaces, relationships, collaborations, and constraints are displayed in the class diagram. It also goes by the name "structural diagram."

Class Notation

A class notation consists of three parts:

1. **Class Name**
 - The first division contains the class's name.
2. **Class Attributes**
 - The second segment presents attributes.
 - After the colon the attribute type is shown.
 - In coding, attributes correspond to member variables (data members).
3. **Class functions (Methods)**
 - In third partition functions are shown. The class offer these services.
 - After the colon at the end of the method signature, a method's return type is displayed
 - After the colon that comes after the parameter name for a method, the return type is displayed.
 - In code class function maps into operations

List of Tour4You Classes:

- Start Slider Class
- Navigation bar Page Class
- My home Class
- Search Page Class
- Review Page Class

- Login Class
- Registration Class
- All Service Class
- Hotel View Class
- Service View Class
- Restaurant View Class
- Transport View Class

Figure 4.2 Class Diagram for Tour4You

Chapter # 5

Physical Data Designing

5.1 Introduction:

The data dictionary and the database's logical and conceptual design are both included in this chapter. The chapter will assist in learning about conceptual and logical design. A data dictionary for the project was provided to help the administrator or reader understand it. This will guarantee database data storage. All the entities and properties will be mentioned.

5.2 Conceptual Design:

All non-aesthetic design management disciplines fall under the broad phrase of conceptual design. To fulfil the vision and endless possibilities, a designer will use their understanding of people, products, services, processes, and profitability. Each will serve as a different color on the designer's canvas. Designing interactions, experiences, procedures, and strategies falls under this category. Conceptual designers are frequently better able to employ abstract reasoning in any situation, are quick to identify the root causes of failure, and are able to understand and relate to the human variables that affect how any system, experience, or interaction affects its users.

Since the emergence of design thinking as a tool for business and research development, many conventionally trained aesthetic designers have been mistakenly asked to assist organizations with workshops pertaining specifically to business or process development in the false belief that all design is equal in this capacity. This has cast a large shadow over design's role in business and development, and questions about design's utility as a tool for company and research development have been raised.

The process of creating a thorough data model or database to satisfy a user's needs is known as database design.

Physical concerns are used in the process of building a data model for each perspective on the real-world situation.

This step involves:

- Building the ER Model
- Verify the model for redundant parts.
- Testing the model against user transactions to make sure it supports all the situations

5.3 Physical Design:

We used the firebase Database for our Application. Which consist of multiple collections like the hotel, transport, event, etc. and we used nested collection for data relationship.

5.4 Tour4You Database:

We created a database and named it “Tour4You” and created nine collections inside this database. Each collection stores different data.

Figure 5.1 Tour4You Database

5.4.1 Event collection:

Information about Events will be stored in this collection. We have two entries in this event collection and each entry have different attributes such as description, district, event, Id, etc.

Figure 5.2 Event Collection

5.4.2 Guidance collection:

Information about Guidance will be stored in this collection. We have one entry in this Guidance collection and it has different attributes such as an address, contact, email, Id, etc.

Figure 5.3 Guidance Collection

5.4.3 Hotel collection:

Information about Hotel will be stored in this collection. We have two entries in this Hotel collection and each entry have different attributes such as description, district, contact, etc. and also has nested collections such as Facilities, review, and Room type.

Figure 5.4 Hotel Collection

5.4.4 Nested collection in Hotel collection:

This is the nested collection of hotel collections named Facilities. It has one entry and has different attributes such as ac, breakfast, heater, etc.

Figure 5.5 Nested Collection in Hotel Collection

5.4.5 Restaurants collection:

Information about Restaurants will be stored in this collection. We have one entry in this restaurant's collection and it has different attributes such as an address, contact, email, Id, etc.

Figure 5.6 Restaurant Collection

5.4.6 Review collection:

Information about the Review will be stored in this collection. We have three entries in this Review collection and each entry have different attributes such as date_and_time, message, name, etc.

Figure 5.7 Review Collection

5.4.7 Tourist Spots collection:

Information about tourist Spots will be stored in this collection. We have two entries in this collection and it has different attributes such as description, district, image, Id, etc.

Figure 5.8 Tourist Spots Collection

5.4.8 Transport collection:

Information about transport will be stored in this collection. We have one entry in this collection and it has different attributes such as company, description, district, image, Id, etc.

Figure 5.9 Transport Collection

5.4.9 User collection:

Information about the User will be stored in this collection. We have one entry in this collection and it has different attributes such as contact, address, email, etc.

Figure 5.10 User Collection

5.5 Entities of the Project:

An entity is a single person, place, or thing that can have data saved about them in connection to a database. An entity is a type of data object that can be categorized and has explicit connections to other entities. An entity is anything that has an existence of its own, whether it is actual or potential, concrete or abstract, physical or not. It is not required to be physical. Particularly, entities are frequently thought to include abstractions and legal fiction. Additionally, there is generally no assumption that a creature is real or alive.

These are some Entities that were used in the Tour4You:

- User
- Hotel
- Transport
- District
- Guidance Companies
- Tourist spots
- Hike and Track
- Restaurants
- Events
- Tour Packages
- Hotel Facilities
- Transport Facilities

5.5.1 Properties of “USER Entity”

User Entity consist of User ID, Full Name, Email, Contact, Address, and Password attributes. ‘User ID’ is the Primary key in user entity.

Figure 5.11 (User Entity)

5.5.2 Properties of “Transport Entity”

Transport Entity consist of ID, Name, District, Email, Contact, Description, Company Name, and Image attributes. ‘ID’ is the Primary key in this entity.

Figure 5.12 (Transport Entity)

5.5.3 Properties of “Hotel Entity”

Hotel Entity consist of Hotel ID, Name, District, Email, Contact, Description, Location, Price and Image attributes. ‘Hotel ID’ is the Primary key in this entity.

Figure 5.13 (Hotel Entity)

5.5.4 Properties of “District Entity”

District Entity consist of Id, Name, District, Description, and Image attributes. ‘Id’ is the Primary key in this entity.

Figure 5.14 (District Entity)

5.5.5 Properties of “Guidance Companies Entity”

Guidance Entity consist of ID, Name, District, Contact, Description, and Image attributes. ‘ID’ is the Primary key in this entity.

Figure 5.15 (Guidance Companies Entity)

5.5.6 Properties of “Tourist Spot Entity”

Tourist Spot Entity consist of Id, Name, Description, Location, Restaurants and Image attributes. ‘Id’ is the Primary key in this entity.

Figure 5.16 (Tourist spot Entity)

5.5.7 Properties of “Hike and Track Entity”

Hike and Track Entity consist of Id, Name, Description, Location and Image attributes. ‘Id’ is the Primary key in this entity.

Figure 5.17 (Hike and track Entity)

5.5.8 Properties of “Restaurants Entity”

Restaurants Entity consist of ID, Name, District, Email, Contact, Description, Location, Tourist Spot, Address and Image attributes. ‘Id’ is the Primary key in this entity.

Figure 5.18 (Restaurants Entity)

5.5.9 Properties of “Events Entity”

Event Entity consist of Id, Name, District, Description, Location, Duration and Image attributes. ‘Id’ is the Primary key in this entity.

Figure 5.19 (Events Entity)

5.5.10 Properties of “Tour Packages Entity”

Tour Packages Entity consist of ID, Name, Description, Price per Person, Price per Couple, Main Attractions, Date, Departure Place, Detail Itinerary, Services Include, Services not Include, ad Image attributes. ‘ID’ is the Primary key in this entity.

Figure 5.20 (Tour Packages Entity)

5.5.11 Properties of “Hotel Facilities Entity”

Hotel Facilities Entity consist of multiple attributes. ‘Id’ is the Primary key in this entity.

Figure 5.21 (Hotel Facilities Entity)

5.5.12 Properties of “Transport Facilities Entity”

Transport Facilities Entity consist of multiple attributes. ‘Id’ is the Primary key in this entity.

Figure 5.22 (Transport Facilities Entity)

5.6 ERD of Tour4You:

This diagram shows the relationship between entities with each other. In this given ERD the entities are logically related to each other. There two types of relations in the given ERD. Some entities have one to one Relationship with other entities while some have one to many relationship. The user entity has relation with transport, Review, Hotel, Guidance, Restaurant, Event and tourist spots. Then transport further have relationship with facilities and review while restaurants has relationship with Reviews and menu. The hotel entity have relation with room type, Facilities and Review. User have one to many relationship with review while others have one to many relation.

Figure 5.23 ERD of Tour4You

CHAPTER # 6

TESTING

6.1 Introduction:

Software requirements analysis is the stage in which we evaluate each demand that we have gathered from users and the market in order to develop a software system. And we arrange all of the requirements in the right sequence to analyze whether or not they are accurate in accordance with how they intersect with the software. We can also add or remove requirements as needed to create any software system.

6.2 Testing Functions:

- Admin Login Form
- Admin Services Management
- Admin Booking Reservation
- User Login Form
- Service Booking
- Comment Box

6.3 Test case for Admin:

These are test cases of all those activities which admin perform.

6.3.1 Admin Login Form:

The Admin login form is functioning correctly, as indicated in the Table. Success in the test.

S. No	Test Case id	Test case Name	Test Case Description	Steps	Expected Result	Actual Result	Test Case Status pass/fail
1	Login Admin	Validate Username And Password	To verify Username and Password in login form	Enter your username and password and click on the login button	Login Successful or an error message "Please Provide Valid Username and Password "	Login Successful	Pass

					must be displayed		
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“Table 6.1 Admin Login Form”

Verification: Its Verify Full “Admin Login Form”.

Environment: Android Mobile.

Test By: Saad Ali.

6.3.2 Admin Services Management Form:

The Admin Services management is functioning correctly, as indicated in the Table. Success in the test.

S. No	Test Case id	Test case Name	Test Case Description	Steps	Expected Result	Actual Result	Test Case Status pass/fail
1	Login Admin	Services Data	To Insert, Update, Delete, View and Save Services Data.	Enter accurate data of Services and click on the button	If data is valid show the message” Data Uploaded or Deleted or Inserted or Saved successfully” If data is not valid show the message “Please Provide Valid Data” must be displayed.	Successful	Pass

“Table 6.2 Admin Services Management”

Verification: Its Verify Full “Admin Service Management”.

Environment: Android Mobile.

Test By: Saad Ali.

6.3.3 Admin Booking Confirmation:

The Admin Booking Reservation is functioning correctly, as indicated in the Table. Success in the test.

S. No	Test Case id	Test case Name	Test Case Description	Steps	Expected Result	Actual Result	Test Case Status pass/fail
1	Login Admin	Booking Data	To Manage Booking Data	Checking Availability and Click on Confirm button	If Service is available show the message "Booking successfully" If Service is not available show the message "Sorry Service is full" must be displayed.	Successful	Pass

"Table 6.3 Admin Booking Confirmation"

Verification: Its Verify Full "Admin Booking Confirmation".

Environment: Android Mobile.

Test By: Bashir Ullah Khan.

6.4 Test case for User

There are test cases for user activities

6.4.1 User Login Form:

The User Login Form is functioning correctly, as indicated in the Table. Success in the test.

S. No	Test Case id	Test case Name	Test Case Description	Steps	Expected Result	Actual Result	Test Case Status pass/fail
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1	Login User	Validate Username And Password	To verify Username and Password in login from	Enter your username and password and click on the login button	Login Successful or an error message "Please Provide Valid Username and Password " must be displayed	Login Successful	Pass
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"Table 6.4 User Login Form"

Verification: Its Verify Full "User Login Form".

Environment: Android Mobile.

Test By: Saad Ali.

6.4.2 User Service Booking

The User service Booking is functioning correctly, as indicated in the Table. Success in the test.

S. No	Test Case id	Test case Name	Test Case Description	Steps	Expected Result	Actual Result	Test Case Status pass/fail
1	User login	Booking Service	To Book or reserve Services Data.	Select your service, visit service, Click on the Book button and complete the payment	If payment is successful show the message" Your Service is successfully booked" If data is not valid show the message "Payment lease Provide Valid Data" must be displayed.	Successful	Pass

"Table 6.5 User Service Booking"

Verification: Its Verify Full “User Service Booking”.

Environment: Android Mobile.

Test By: Saad Ali.

6.4.3 User Comment

The User Comment is functioning correctly, as indicated in the Table. Success in the test.

S. No	Test Case id	Test case Name	Test Case Description	Steps	Expected Result	Actual Result	Test Case Status pass/fail
1	User Login	User Comment	To Check Comment whether it working or not.	Select feedback, the select on comment box and write your feedback and click on the comment Button.	Comment Successful	Successful	Pass

“Table 6.6 User comment”

Verification: Its Verify Full “User Comment”.

Environment: Android Mobile.

Test By: Bashir Ullah Khan.

Chapter # 7

User Interface / User Guide

7.1 System Installation:

Our Android App is available on Play store and can simply download and Install on any Android mobile. The interface of our App is simple so everyone can use it very easily.

7.2 Start Slider:

When you open the APP this page will be shown. This is a simple starting page where our services are advertised through Image Slider.

Figure 7.1 Start Slider

7.3 Home Page:

All information is available on the home page such as login, search bar, our services, promotions, tourist spots, etc. if someone looking for Hotel they just click on Hotel and they will be shifted to the Hotel page. The same method is applied to the rest of all.

Figure 7.2 Home Page

7.4 Navigation Drawer:

The navigation drawer in the APP allows users to navigate to different pages of your APP. It can be opened by clicking on the menu icon in the app bar.

Figure 7.3 Navigation Drawer

7.5 Login page:

On the login page simply just enter your email and password and enter the App. If you are new just click on sign up you will be shifted to the sign up page. In the top right in red color is for Admin login.

Figure 7.4 Login Page

7.6 Sign up page:

Here you need to fill out the form for registration. Some questions will be asked from you here like name, email, password, etc. And you also need to read the terms and conditions.

Figure 7.5 Sign-up Page

7.7 Hotels page:

On this page all hotel information is present. If someone is looking for a hotel in swat they click on Swat and all the hotels in Swat will appear on this page. The same is for Chitral and others.

Figure 7.6 Hotels Page

7.8 Transport page:

On this page all Travel information is present. If someone is looking for Transport in swat they click on Swat and all the travels in Swat will appear on this page. The same is for Chitral and others.

Figure 7.7 Transport Page

7.9 Tourist spots:

On this page all Tourist spots are present. If someone is looking for Tourist Spot in swat they click on Swat and all the Tourist spots in Swat will appear on this page. The same is for Chitral and others.

Figure 6.8 Tourist Spots

7.10 Guidance page:

On this page all Guidance companies are present. If someone is looking for Tour Guidance in swat they click on Swat and all the Guidance companies in Swat will appear on this page. The same is for Chitral and others.

Figure 7.9 Guidance Page

7.11 Events page:

On this page all information about Events is present. If someone is looking for Events in different areas they click on that place and all the events happening in that place will appear on the screen.

Figure 7.10 Events Page

7.12 Restaurants Page:

On this page all information about the Restaurants is present. If someone is looking for Restaurants in Swat they click on Swat and all the Restaurants in Swat will appear on this page. The same is for Chitral and others.

Figure 7.11 Restaurants page

7.13 Hotel page:

If you like one Hotel on the Hotels page and you click on that Hotel this page will be shown. On this page Details, Facilities, Reviews, and Directions of the Hotel will be present. In the Detail section Description of the Hotel, Rooms types, Rooms Prices, Room availability, etc. are available. Here also you can book your Room. In the Facilities section you can see which facilities offer the Hotel. In Reviews Section you can give your review and also see others people's reviews about the Hotel. In the Directions section just click on Get Direction Button and you will be shifted to Map.

Figure 7.12 Hotel Page

7.14 Transport Booking page:

On this page information about the transport company will be available. The description, Facilities, and Reviews about this Transport Company will available on this page and you can also book vehicles from this page.

Figure 7.13 Transport Booking Page

7.15 Guidance Company Booking Page:

On this page information about the Guidance, Company will be available and here you can also book or hire a Guider for your trip.

Figure 7.14 Guidance Company Booking Page

7.16 Restaurant Page:

On this page all information about the Restaurant is available. The description and contact are available in the **Details** section. Foods that are available in Restaurant are present in **Menu** Section and the location of the Restaurant is present in the **Direction** section.

Figure 7.15 Restaurant Page

7.17 Search Page:

This is a search page where you can search places, hotels, tourist spots, etc.

Figure 7.16 Search Page

7.18 Our Team page:

This page represent Tour4you team members and their information.

Figure 7.17 Our team Page

Chapter # 8

DEVELOPMENT TOOLS

8.1 Introduction

We have used the following tools on our proposed project during design and development.

8.2 Flutter

Google created the cross-platform software development kit (SDK) for building mobile apps called Flutter. To create apps for Android and iOS devices, Flutter employs use the Dart programming language. A single code base may be used to create apps with a native look and feel on both Android and iOS devices because it is cross-platform.

8.3 Dart

A programming language called Dart was created specifically for client development, including web and mobile apps. It was created by Google and may be used to create desktop and server apps.

8.4 Firebase Database

The Firebase Real-Time Database is a NoSQL database hosted in the cloud that provides real-time data synchronization and storage between users. When an app is offline, the data is still accessible because it is continuously synced across all clients.

8.5 Visual Studio Code

Microsoft created the source-code editor known as Visual Studio Code, often known as VS Code, for Windows, Linux, and macOS. Among the features are debugging assistance, syntax highlighting, intelligent code completion, snippets, code refactoring, and embedded Git. Users can install extensions, alter preferences, and modify the theme and keyboard shortcuts.

8.6 Figma

The desktop programs for macOS and Windows provide additional offline features in the collaborative browser-based interface design tool known as Figma. On mobile and tablet devices, the Figma mobile app for Android and iOS enables real-time viewing and interaction with Figma prototypes. Figma's feature set concentrates on real-time collaboration, user interface and user experience design, and a variety of vector graphics editors and prototype tools.

8.7 Adobe Illustrator

Adobe publishes Adobe Illustrator, a tool for modifying vector graphics. It is helpful for creating exact, resolution-independent images such as logos, clip art, blueprints, and others.

Chapter # 9

Summary and Future Work

9.1 Summary:

Tour4You is a complete tourism market. Tour4You provide multiple Services (Online Hotel booking, Transport booking, Guidance, Tour packages, restaurant reservation, and customize tour packages) under one umbrella. Tourist can easy book our services from home and can feel free about services.

Tourist can also see information about tourist spots, events and weather through our mobile Application. User can also use maps option to navigate into his destination.

9.2 Future Work:

Later on in this Application we will new features which are following,

- An Option of Maps which will navigate user from current location to its destination.
- An option for Online payment.
- An option for traditional products shopping
- A Services of Full Customize Packages

- **References:**

We use the following references to complete the project.

1. <https://www.flutter.com>.
2. <https://firebase.google.com/>
3. <https://dart.dev/>
4. <https://www.canva.com/>
5. <https://www.figma.com/>